

Study of Prognostic Significance of Serum Levels of Creatine Kinase in OPP. Importance of Elevated Serum Amylase in Patients of Organophosphorus Compound Poisoning

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Abstract:

Background: Organophosphate poisoning is a ever increasing and troublesome situation in the developing countries and is a major health care challenge in the 21st century. Organophosphates are extremely toxic chemicals which present with a myriad of clinical problems all of which lead to difficulties in determining management. The organophosphates are an extremely toxic group of compounds which are rapidly absorbed by the dermal and oral routes. Following significant exposure symptoms of toxicity generally occur within 4 hours.

Aim: Study of prognostic significance of serum levels of Creatine kinase in OPP. Importance of elevated serum amylase in patients of organophosphorus compound poisoning.

Method: This is a cross sectional study of 50 patients with OP poisoning admitted at government hospital medical ward, Kurnool. The severity of poisoning, important biochemical, clinical parameters were measured. Serum CPK, serum amylase and serum acetylcholinesterase were collected at admission and during follow-up in all patients. The outcome studied would be survival with or without ventilator assistance and death.

Results: Among 50 poisoning patients, 68% being male and 48% aged between 21-40 years. Most patients (76%) were married, and farmers constituted the largest occupational group (34%). Chlorpyrifos and Dimethoate were the most common poisons, accounting for 30% and 28% of cases. In terms of clinical findings, 60% of patients had SpO₂ levels above 95%, and 48% had serum Creatine phosphokinase (CPK) levels below 350 U/L, while 26% had CPK levels above 1400 U/L. Serum amylase was normal in 72% of cases, and 56% had elevated plasma acetylcholinesterase (AChE) levels. Ventilator support was needed in 46% of patients, especially those with higher CPK levels. Chi-square tests indicated significant associations between elevated CPK, amylase, and AChE levels with poorer outcomes, including higher mortality.

Conclusion: The biochemical marker serum amylase & Creatine kinase is a dependable indicator due to its accessibility, affordability, and ability to forecast the need for intubation and mortality in cases of acute OP-poisoning. Elevated serum amylase & creatine kinase levels reported at admission indicate a worse prognosis and a higher likelihood of death. Therefore, it can serve as an alternative indicator for predicting clinical outcome and prognosis.

Keywords: Organophosphorus compound, Anticholinesterase, Creatine phosphokinase, serum amylase.

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Introduction

Organophosphates have been used as pesticides worldwide for over 50 years. [1] Owing to their high toxicity, their usage has decreased in the last 10 to 20 years. In the treatment of glaucoma, myasthenia gravis, and Alzheimer's disease, organophosphates such as neostigmine, edrophonium, pyridostigmine, echothiophate, tacrine, and donepezil are employed to reverse neuromuscular inhibition. [2] Over 3,000,000 individuals, both male and female, are subjected to foreign exposure annually, resulting in a remarkable 300,000 deaths. [3] First and foremost, by contact with agricultural

chemicals. Other factors contributing to poisoning include the ingestion of infected food and the wearing of contaminated clothing. [4] The chemical chlorpyrifos is found in a diverse selection of well-known roach and ant disinfectants. Since 2001, the US Environmental Protection Agency (EPA) has prohibited the home use of chlorpyrifos. [5] During the 1940s, Germany developed several organophosphorus nerve poisons, including tabun [GA], sarin [GB], and soman [GD]. However, these poisons have not been used for military purposes. The global concern lies in the prevention, detection, and

treatment of organophosphorus ("nerve") agent-related mortality. [6] Elevated levels of Serum Amylase and Serum CPK have been associated with a poor treatment outcome in individuals suffering from acute myocardial infarction, congestive coronary heart failure, stroke, and sepsis. Increased levels of these markers are associated with acute inflammation and heightened oxidative stress, and they are simple and cost-effective diagnostic strategies. [7] The objective is to identify cost-effective and readily quantifiable biomarkers in a nation with limited resources, such as India.

Acetylcholinesterase (AChE) activity in human blood reflects the function of synaptic AChE, which is the main enzyme targeted by anticholinesterase agents. Most organophosphate (OP) compounds inhibit butyrylcholinesterase (BuChE) in plasma more quickly than AChE in erythrocytes, making it necessary to measure both AChE and BuChE for an accurate assessment of OP exposure. Since BuChE is present in plasma and AChE is attached to the erythrocyte membrane, determining the activity of each enzyme requires either separating erythrocytes from plasma or using specific substrates or inhibitors to selectively measure one enzyme in the presence of the other. However, fully selective substrates or inhibitors for AChE or BuChE do not exist, and complete separation of erythrocytes from plasma is difficult without losing some enzyme activity. In cases of acute OP poisoning, serum cholinesterase (ChE) activity is usually reduced within hours or days but returns to normal relatively quickly. Around 3% of the population has a genetic variation that results in a deficiency in serum ChE. Additionally, factors like pregnancy, inflammatory conditions (acute or chronic), neoplasia, certain medications (e.g., succinylcholine, codeine, morphine), malnutrition, and liver disease can affect serum ChE levels, though the reduction caused by these conditions is generally less severe than that from OP insecticide exposure. [8]

Serum amylase is a readily accessible, widely available, and cost-effective biochemical marker for diagnosing acute organophosphate (OP) poisoning. Numerous studies have indicated a higher incidence of pancreatitis and associated complications in individuals exposed to OP compounds compared to the general population. These patients often exhibit elevated serum amylase levels. Although the precise mechanisms underlying this phenomenon are not fully understood, several hypotheses have been proposed. One such theory suggests that OP insecticides increase intraductal pressure and pancreatic exocrine flow, leading to the extravasation of pancreatic fluid. The rise in exocrine pancreatic flow may result from direct cholinergic hyperstimulation of pancreatic acinar and ductal cells. Observations following OP poisoning include pancreatic interstitial oedema, vacuolization of acinar cells,

and elevated levels of serum amylase and lipase. [9]

Three types of muscle injuries (paralysis) are noticed in OP poisoning. Type I is due to continued depolarization at neuro-muscular junction, type II due to intermediate syndrome and type III due to delayed polyneuropathy. The elevated serum CPK levels were confirmed during the acute stage of toxicity i.e. all cases presented within 24 hours of exposure to OP compounds and before the development of the intermediate syndrome. Intermediate syndrome occurs in between the periods of acute and delayed OP toxicity. Intermediate syndrome occurs in patients 24–96 hours after acute OP poisoning. Raised CPK levels occur due to rhabdomyolysis in — intermediate syndrome [10].

Serum Amylase and Serum CPK can serve as prognostic indicators for Organophosphorus toxicity. Pulmonary failure is the primary cause of death in cases of OPC poisoning. Critical respiratory failure caused by acute cholinesterase crisis is the most common complication of OPC poisoning, resulting in mortality. Timely detection of intoxication and immediate respiratory assistance may also improve survival rates. Hence, it is imperative to acknowledge scientific methodologies and criteria for predicting the requirement of ventilatory assistance during the initial assessment. Reduction in serum cholinesterase levels occurs following OPC intoxication. The Peradenya OP compound scale is a simple numerical scale designed to assess the intensity of OPC poisoning. [11] This study examined the medical condition of ventilated patients with OPC poisoning and aimed to establish a correlation between biochemical markers to predict the mortality and morbidity resulting from the poisoning.

The purpose of this work is to determine the role of Serum Amylase and Serum CPK as biochemical indicators in predicting the severity of OPC poisoning in ventilated patients and its outcome.

Aims and Objectives:

- To Study of prognostic significance of serum levels of Creatine kinase in OPP.
- To study the Importance of elevated serum amylase in patients of organophosphorus compound poisoning.

Materials and Methods

Study Design: Study conducted among patients admitted in medicine department, Kurnool Government General Hospital, who are admitted with Organophosphate poisoning all through the length of study May 2023 to April 2024 are enrolled in our study. After acquiring clearance and approval from the institutional ethics committee and written consent of the caregivers, patients admitted to the emergency with organophosphorus compound poi-

soning will be chosen after successful inclusion and exclusion standards and enrolled in the study.

Source of data: This study was conducted at General medicine Department, Government General Hospital Kurnool over one year. Patient presenting to the emergency medical department with acute OP poisoning were included in this study.

Sample size: 50

Duration of study: 1 year

Study design: Observational and prospective study

Inclusion criteria: All ingestional and inhalational op compound poisoning Patients between ages 13 to 60 years with initial clinical assessment.

Exclusion criteria:

1. The subtype of organophosphate poison and their fatal outcomes were not studied separately
2. Recent hemorrhage, chronic liver disease, prior chemotherapy were excluded

As the study had smaller group of population from a single institution, this may not represent the whole country population.

Procedure of Collection of Data: All patients had undergone thorough clinical examination, vital signs like pulse rate, blood pressure, temperature, respiratory rate, conscious levels by GCS and systemic examination were done. Diagnosis of OP poisoning was done bedside by using POP scale.

Investigations for Diagnosing Op Compound Poisoning: Serum Cholinesterase Estimation Principle: Butyrylcholine iodide is hydrolyzed by means of cholinesterase to produce thiocholine in the presence of potassium hex cyanoferrate, the absorbance minimize at 405nm is at once propor-

tional to the cholinesterase activity in the sample. Reagent: RI-Buffer reagent and R II-Butyrylthiocholine iodide reagent Sample: Use non-haemolysin serum, Heparin or EDTA, plasma Reference Level: 4850-12000 U/L Poisoning severity scores: In this study we used Peradeniya organo phosphorus poison scale.

All other investigations were accordingly performed are:

- 1) Serum electrolytes
- 2) Liver and renal function tests
- 3) Serum CPK levels
- 4) Chest X-ray
- 5) Serum amylase
- 6) Serum acetylcholine levels

Treatment

Treatment for the patients was given as per standard protocols, they are as follows briefly:

1. Removal of contaminated clothes and removal of adherent poison
2. Gastric lavage
3. Fluid resuscitation
4. Atropinization
5. Qxime therapy
6. Specific organ support if needed
7. Mechanical ventilation to patients who required.

Statistical Analysis: Data was collected case record forms (case proforma). Data was then entered into EXCEL spreadsheet 2007. Data was described as actual numbers and percentages. Pearsons Chi-square test was used to calculate the test of significance. All statistical analysis was performed using SPSS20. A two-tailed 'p' value of <0.05 was considered significant statistically,

Results:

Table 1: Demographic and other variables of patients

Particulars		Observations N (%)
Gender	Male	34(68%)
	Female	16(32%)
Age Group (years)	Upto 20 yrs	4 (8%)
	21 - 30 yrs	12(24%)
	31 - 40 yrs	12 (24%)
	41 - 50 yrs	10 (20%)
	51 - 60 yrs	8 (16%)
	Above 60 yrs	4 (8%)
Marital status	Married	38 (76%)
	Unmarried	12 (24%)
Occupation	Coolie	5 (10%)
	Farmer	17(34%)
	Homemaker	10(20%)
	Private	5 (10%)
	Student	8 (16%)
	Unemployed	5 (10%)
Composition of poison	Chlorpryphos	15 (30%)

	Dimethoate	14 (28%)
	Endosulfan	5 (10%)
	Malathion	5 (10%)
	Monocrotophos	11 (22%)
Area	Rural	23 (46%)
	Semiurban	13 (26%)
	Urban	14 (28%)
Pulse rate	40 - 60	11 (22%)
	61 - 80	25(50%)
	81 - 100	13 (26%)
	> 100	1 (1%)
Respiratory rate	16 - 26	39 (78%)
	27 - 32	5(10%)
	> 32	6 (12%)
Ventilation support	No	27 (54%)
	Yes	23(46%)
Outcome	Dead	10 (20%)
	Discharged	40 (80%)

The data outlines the demographic and clinical characteristics of 50 poisoning patients. Among them, 68% are male and 32% are female. Most patients fall within the 21-40 age group (48%), while only 8% are above 60 years.

A large proportion (76%) are married. Occupational distribution shows that farmers constitute the largest group (34%), followed by homemakers

(20%). Chlorpyrifos and Dimethoate are the most common poisons, accounting for 30% and 28% of cases, respectively.

In terms of geographic distribution, 46% of the patients are from rural areas, with a similar number requiring ventilation support (46%). The majority of patients (80%) were discharged, while 20% succumbed to the poisoning.

Table 2: Observation of different evaluation parameters of patients

Particulars		Observations N (%)	
Oxygen Saturation (SpO ₂)	< 85	3 (6%)	
	85 - 90	7 (14%)	
	91 - 95	10 (20%)	
	> 95	30 (60%)	
Serum Creatine phosphokinase (CPK)	< 350	24 (48%)	
	350 - 700	3 (6%)	
	701 - 1050	5 (10%)	
	1051 - 1400	5 (10%)	
	> 1400	13 (26%)	
Serum Amylase	25-130	36(72%)	
	>130	14(28%)	
Plasma Acetylcholinesterase (AChE)	501 - 1000	5 (10%)	
	1001 - 1500	7 (14%)	
	1501 - 2000	7 (14%)	
	2001 - 2500	3 (6%)	
	> 2500	28(56%)	
		Ventilator support	
		Yes	No
CPK	<350	1 (2%)	20 (40%)
	350 - 700	1 (2%)	3 (6%)
	701 - 1050	5 (10%)	2 (4%)
	1051 - 1400	4 (8%)	0 (0%)
	> 1400	13 (26%)	1 (2%)
		Chi square 30.54 P <0.05 significant	
		Death	Discharge
Comparison of serum CPK with the outcome	< 350	0 (0%)	22 (44%)
	350 - 700	1 (2%)	3 (6%)
	701 - 1050	0 (0%)	6 (12%)

	1051 - 1400	2 (4%)	3 (6%)
	> 1400	7(14%)	6 (12%)
	Chi square 17.62 P <0.05 significant		
Amylase	25-130	1(2%)	31(62%)
	>130	9(18%)	9(18%)
	Chi square 15.82 P <0.05 significant		
AChE	501 - 1000	2 (4%)	3 (6%)
	1001 - 1500	3 (6%)	4 (8%)
	1501 - 2000	2 (4%)	5 (10%)
	2001 - 2500	1 (2%)	3 (6%)
	> 2500	1 (2%)	25 (50%)
	Chi square 8.62 P <0.05 significant		

The table highlights key clinical and biochemical parameters in poisoning patients. Oxygen saturation levels indicate that 60% of patients had SpO₂ > 95%, while 6% had critically low levels below 85%. Serum Creatine phosphokinase (CPK) was elevated (>1400 U/L) in 26% of patients, while 48% had levels below 350 U/L. Serum amylase was normal in 72% of patients, with the remainder showing elevated levels. Plasma acetylcholinesterase (AChE) was >2500 U/L in 56% of cases. Ventilator support was required by 46% of patients, especially those with high CPK levels. Chi-square tests revealed significant associations (p < 0.05) between elevated CPK, amylase, and AChE levels with ventilator support, mortality, and patient outcomes. Elevated CPK and AChE levels were correlated with poorer outcomes, including higher mortality rates.

Discussion:

Organophosphorus poisoning can result in potentially fatal conditions, such as respiratory failure. Organo-phosphorus compounds are widely used in India as pesticides, with the majority of users being suicidal due to their accessibility. Patients and critical care professionals must immediately identify and treat these chemicals' toxicity. There are occasional case reports describing the clinical importance of the total blood CPK level and serum amylase in acute OP poisoning. Still, no extensive research has been done on the total CPK level and serum amylase in OP compound poisoning. Thus, an effort has been made to investigate the clinical relevance of Creatine kinase and serum amylase in OP chemical poisoning.

The present study was conducted for two years, from May 2023 to April 2024, in Department of Medicine, Government General Hospital Kurnool. The study's epidemiology, clinical profile and outcome were compared with various distinguished literature. The present study showed that Among 50 patients 68% are male and 32% are female. Most patients fall within the 21-40 age group (48%), while only 8% are above 60 years. This is similar to other studies Anbuselvam

Bharathisezhian et al [12], Rayannavar et al. [13] and Hassan et al. [14]

A large proportion (76%) are married. Occupational distribution shows that farmers constitute the largest group (34%), followed by homemakers (20%) In terms of geographic distribution, 46% of the patients are from rural areas, with a similar number requiring ventilation support (46%). Anbuselvam Bharathisezhian et al and Weismann-Brenner et al [15] also reported similar findings in their investigations

Chlorpyrifos and Dimethoate are the most common poisons, accounting for 30% and 28% of cases, respectively. This is similar to other studies Anbuselvam Bharathisezhian et al. The majority of patients (80%) were discharged, while 20% succumbed to the poisoning. The mortality in the Anbuselvam Bharathisezhian et al was 21 %,

The present study showed that clinical and biochemical parameters in poisoning patients. Oxygen saturation levels indicate that 60% of patients had SpO₂ > 95%, while 6% had critically low levels below 85%. Serum Creatine phosphokinase (CPK) was elevated (>1400 U/L) in 26% of patients, while 48% had levels below 350 U/L.

These findings are in agreement with those of Bhattacharyya et al. [16], who demonstrated that there is a strong association between the initial CPK value and the Peradeniya organophosphorus poisoning (POP) scale, serum AChE levels, arterial pH values, and the total dose of atropine in cases of acute OPC poisoning.

Anbuselvam Bharathisezhian et al study showed that an increase in serum CPK correlates well with the severity of poisoning. A CPK level of more than >1400 was observed, with the highest level in those requiring ventilatory support (28%) and those who expired (81%). The AchE level range of 501 to 1000 was observed with the most patients who died. In the study by Anbuselvam and Bharathisezhian, elevated serum CPK levels were observed during the acute toxicity phase, with all patients presenting within 6 hours of exposure to

organophosphate (OP) compounds, prior to the onset of intermediate syndrome. This finding aligns with the study by Bhattacharyya et al., which demonstrated that serum CPK levels can rise in OPC poisoning patients even in the absence of intermediate syndrome, likely due to muscle fiber necrosis. Intermediate syndrome typically develops between the acute and delayed phases of OPC toxicity, most commonly appearing 24 to 96 hours following acute OPC exposure. On the other hand, John and colleagues brought attention to the fact that muscle injury starts during cholinergic crises, and that the level of muscle injury is proportional to the intensity of the cholinergic crises. The overabundance of acetylcholine that is observed in OPC poisoning causes myocyte damage that can be reversed and an increase in the production of various muscle enzymes, including CPK. [26]

Serum amylase was normal in 72% of patients, with the remainder showing elevated levels.

In Raveendra and Mohan study, [17] severe patients had higher mean serum amylase levels than mild and moderate patients. M E Sumathi et al [18] grouped 53 acute OP-poisoning patients into three plasma ChE activity groups: Group 1 (20%–50% plasma ChE activity) contained 12 patients, 6 of whom (50%) had elevated blood amylase levels and 3 had lipase levels; Group 2 (10%–20% plasma ChE activity) had 15 patients, with 7 (46.66%) with elevated serum amylase levels and 3 with elevated serum lipase levels. Group 3 (<10% plasma ChE activity) had 26 patients, with 19 (73.04%) having elevated serum amylase levels and 6 with elevated serum lipase levels.

Subedi et al. [19] study demonstrated higher mean values of serum amylase level either within 12 h of exposure or 12 h post exposure in participants who became dead during the course of treatment. This shows the serum amylase levels dramatically rises in severe/ life-threatening presentations with OP poisoning which is evident from multiple other studies. [20,21,22], A study by Nagabhiru [23] revealed that there was a significant rise in serum amylase level following OP poisoning and they concluded that serum amylase levels can be considered as marker of organophosphorus intoxication

Plasma acetylcholinesterase (AChE) was >2500 U/L in 56% of cases. Ventilator support was required by 46% of patients, especially those with high CPK levels. Chi-square tests revealed significant associations ($p < 0.05$) between elevated CPK, amylase, and AChE levels with ventilator support, mortality, and patient outcomes. Elevated CPK and AChE levels were correlated with poorer outcomes, including higher mortality rates. This is similar to other studies Anbuselvam Bharathisezhian et al.

A retrospective study done by Lee et al. that included 121 patients with OP poisoning at Veterans General Hospital showed that 44 patients (36%) had elevated amylase levels (serum amylase >360 U/L). [24] The finding of elevated amylase levels was closely related to clinical severity and presence of acute pancreatitis and septic shock. Another study done by N Matsumiya et al. [25] on 32 OP-poisoning patients admitted to the intensive care unit at Kyodo General Hospital, Ibaraki, Japan, in 1996, to analyse the incidence of respiratory failure showed that these patients developed respiratory failure and received ventilator support. An increase in plasma amylase above the normal range was found in patients who developed respiratory failure. [25]

Therefore, biochemical markers concerning OPC intoxication, such as serum CPK. And serum amylase, which are readily available, affordable, and easily quantifiable, can be utilized in the process of forecasting and evaluating the prognosis of patients who have acquired OPC poisoning.

Conclusion:

Organophosphorus poisoning is prevalent in India, particularly affecting males aged 21–40, with 46% of cases requiring ventilatory support. Elevated serum CPK levels are strongly correlated with the severity of poisoning, particularly during the acute phase. Serum amylase levels rise significantly in severe cases, though 72% of patients displayed normal levels. Plasma AChE exceeded 2500 U/L in 56% of cases, with adverse outcomes linked to elevated CPK and AChE levels. Serum CPK and amylase are crucial biochemical markers for predicting the prognosis of OPC poisoning.

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